

OBSERVER RECORDING SHEET FOR USER STUDY “MAINTAINING HIERARCHICAL CONTROL APPLICATIONS WITH 4DIAC IDE”

Interviewee: _____ Date: _____

Observer: _____

TASK	OBSERVATIONS AND COMMENTS
#0 Setup	
TASK 1	ORIENTING IN AN UNKNOWN APPLICATION
1.1 Overview of the application	
1.2 Follow connection	
TASK 2	CREATING/REMOVING HIERARHIES
2.1 Create subapp from existing network	
2.2 Add block to subapp	
2.3 Delete subapp hierarchy	

TASK 3	WORKING WITH TYPES
3.1 Save subapplication as type	
3.2 Import subapplication	
3.3 Replace subapplication from 3.1	
TASK 4	EDITING
4.1 Detach subapplication from type	
4.2 Edit Interface	
4.3 Add blocks	
4.4 Create connections	
General Observations	